

CULTURAL SCIENCES

WHAT IS THE NEXT STEP AFTER THE NEW MUSEUM DEFINITION?

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Abstract

The new museum definition presents modern approach to the museum as an “Not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society... They operate and communicate ethically professionally and with the participation of communities...”. Corporation of the professionals after many years of discussion have fixed in this definition an understanding of the museums’ role in society that has been developed in the recent decades: without the participation of communities the museum cannot valuably fulfill its function. How deep does this interaction change the concept of traditional museum? What strategies does the professional corporation select here? What the new concepts will appear in the museology as a result of the new definition of the museum? Let’s try to answer these questions.

Keywords: new museum’s form, social institute, deconstruction, decolonisation, indigenous community.

Introduction

The latest publications of International Committee of museology of ICOM under the auspices of the fight against tradition in museology have presented a wide panorama of radical innovations in museum practice. An analysis of two editions – “Decolonising Museology: Museums, Community Action and Decolonisation”, and “The Decolonisation of Museology: Museums, Mixing, and Myths of Origin” – allows us to conclude that significant transformation occurs in the museum landscape. The articles contained in these publications describe how certain social groups that are not discontented with the existing representation of their identity in society solve their problems through museum forms and, among other things, as a result of ICOM recommendations that new actors guide.

The flexible form of the museum permits community members to develop an activity about meaningful values including native territory, attitude to one's own body, local history, customs and traditions. The involvement in the dissemination of varied values is a universal characteristic that allows the actors of new museum forms to typologize themselves as a museum and rank among such museums as eco-museums, open-air museums, museums of communities/schools/corporations, museums in indigenous lands, mobile museums, online museums, etc. On the other hand, in the context of activities about these values, which allow uniting in social groups, the museum begins to play the role of a full-fledged social institution.

The innovations that have been described in the papers of these two editions have presented the changes of understanding the role of the heritage institution which occurred largely under the ideas of the New Museology. The 2001 UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity and the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage were

the documentary basis for an even wider practical application the ideas of the New Museology. The last document became especially significant, switching the attention of museum specialists from collecting and studying collections to interacting with the local community, folklore sphere, customs and traditions. This inevitably turned the museum outside, prompted it to go beyond the boundaries of professional walls and, as a result, there was an erasure the opposition between the museum staff and visitors, staff and local communities, staff and donators. And this trend is growing stronger today, turning the museum into a full-fledged social institution.

Using the relevant term

First of all, I would like to comment on the term decolonization, which have been used in order to describe recent changes in the museum sphere during last years in the issues published by ICOFOM. This term has political coloration and transfers the discussion out of culturology context thus overshadowing consideration of the sociocultural foundations of the transformation in the museum field. The term decolonization has been used by politology for description of struggle of colonies for freedom from metropolises (Makarenko 2012, 6-47). Then the question arises how adequate is the borrowing of this term for museology? How correctly does it describe the real changes that are taking place in the museum landscape?

In bare outlines, a wide panorama of changes in the museum sphere described by colleagues in the two editions of ICOFOM “Decolonising Museology: Museums, Community Action and Decolonisation”, and “The Decolonisation of Museology: Museums, Mixing, and Myths of Origin” have demonstrate that the term decolonization is perceived by the authors as an opportunity to apply a fundamentally different approach to the analysis of modern museum practice, aimed at democratizing museums. At the same time, the emphasis

is on practice in a broader, cultural level, without regard by the framework of the traditional museum field. This approach has become a platform to help reflect on the new integrative nature of the ensemble of relationships around the museum in response to the insistent-sounding demands for renewal on the part of new actors that have become involved in the museum activities in the past decade. These activities have changed the museum landscape so much that we can talk about the deconstruction of the museum as an institution of cultural heritage. On this term that I would like to emphasize, as opposed to the term decolonization used by my colleagues.

In the scientific sense, the very term decolonization, which has a political connotation, implies the replacement of some actors by others who have achieved leadership positions, and the elimination of losers. (Rostova 2020, p. 734). I don't think the ICOFOM leaders have such a radical approach in mind when they used the term decolonization. While the term deconstruction is widely used in contemporary philosophy and art to denote the overcoming of stereotypes and the inclusion of innovations that can create a new context. This term will allow to analyze the current changes in the museum landscape remaining in the field of cultural studies, without moving into the field of political science. And for this reason, it is worth to exclude the use of the term decolonization when discussing the current situation in museum.

Let's try to comprehend the culturological foundations of changes which described in the articles of two ICOFOM editions through deconstruction term.

The activities of indigenous communities

The activity of local communities which have become real actors in recent times, on a new round have initiated another phase of the social experiment. In Brazil this movement supported by the National Museum Policy (2003). The Local Memory Program was developed by the activity of the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Justice and the Brazilian Institute of Museums. They have promoted museological procedures among indigenous communities helping to manifest their identity. The self-government, self-reflection and indigenous authorship were the main goals of this policy (Cury 2020, pp. 75-79). As a result, a variety of new experimental form of a museum without a collection, a museum not aimed at visitors, but focused on the local community was born.

Thus, in the article "As pegadas inventadas pelo Museu Vivo do São Bento na Baixada Fluminense" was told the story of an unusual museum (Carias & Souza & Nogueira 2020 pp.160-175). The districts territory of the Duque de Caxias and Recôncavo Guanabara, which are located in a poor suburb of Rio de Janeiro, has been visited by students, teachers for more than 20 years. And in 2008, by the request of specialists in the field of education, history and culture a municipal museum within the framework of experimental museology aimed at study local history was organized.

This museum is conceived as a "place of human experience." It situated in the old district with elements of the village, archaeological excavations dating back to the 4th-6th millennium BC, colonial buildings of the

19th century such as a farm on Iguazu, Nossa Senhora do chapels, and other buildings of the post-colonial period. The museum consists of a team of educators and historians working in the educational public network of the Duque de Caxias. It exists as a collection of pedagogical routes with main and secondary ones which based on the techniques of experimental museology. The main idea is the search for meanings, the acquisition of new ways of interpreting reality in the learning the territory, where trace of the period of slavery, the republic and the present time have been preserved. The visit is guided by a teacher who offers a critical reading of the trajectories of human destiny, struggle, resistance and conformation. The authors write that in the process of interpretation the places of memory acquire the status of historical and cultural values, a heritage that must be preserved. The museum became a means of self-identification of residents with their place, gave legitimacy to the local community, who was excluded from official history.

Approximately similar position of "the desire of the museum" in the implementation of their rights of minorities is demonstrated by the activists of the "Museu da Parteira", whose activities are considered by the authors of the article as "an experimental process in constant transformation, driven by the will and traditional knowledge of midwives in the state of Pernambuco" (Morim 2020, pp. 193-212).

These forms of the social community museum, the paramuseum (Peter van Mensch's term) have become a powerful means of social and cultural transformation within the local territory. About the diversity of such museums, which appeared in Brazil, Chile, Mexico and Colombia is described in the articles of the edition with characteristic titles: "Os índios Tikuna e o mundo dos Museus" (Faulhaber 2020, pp. 91-102), "Museu das Remoções: Moradia e Memória" (Teixeira 2020, pp. 226-238), "Memórias silenciadas e novos horizontes: O papel social do Museu do Samba" (Santos 2020, pp.213-225) and so on. All these museums have adapted various forms of museum activity to the needs of local communities and they have become a flexible tool that provides an adequate form of solving the social problems of the community.

It should be noted that earlier the organization of museums within the framework of the New Museology (eco-museums, ethno-museums, community museums) was carried out by researchers (anthropologists, ethnographers, museologists), only involving the local community in their work. Now the initiative has passed to the indigenous persons: they are not contented with only participation and are sought to find their voice in order to more accurately speak about of their worldview, understanding their temporality, duration and life cycles.

I would like to remind that the museum usually implemented the function of their significant values presenting by certain social groups on the public stage. We emphasize that the museum was not modus of socialization, it was a method of presentation. In this case, it is clear that the situation has fundamentally changed: the museum is used as an organizational form that allows through the actualization of one's traditions and

cultural patterns to outline the boundaries of a social group and thereby reaffirm one's place in society. The practice of experimental museology, focused primarily on the internal problems of the community, turns the museum into a full-fledged social institution. Its main function is the institutionalization of behavior patterns of people living in the neighborhood, based on self-identification. Actualization of intangible cultural heritage, its interpretation, its transmission to future generations, expansion of the range of carriers through the consolidation of behavioral patterns – this is the main task of the community museum. But these are the characteristics of a social institution! And in this case, we see how the traditional professional museum institution acquires a new function, transforms in order to confirm its viability. This is in accordance with the reflections of Pieter van Mensch and Leontina Meyer about the prevalence of integrative tendencies in the modern world, about museum 3.0 (Mensch, Meijer 2021, pp.77-81).

The activities of LGBT+

Following indigenous communities, representatives of the sexual minorities and LGBT+ defend their right to organize museums. The articles published in edition present “traces of experience that cannot be included in any academic publications” as Brulon Soares notes but they testify “to a new time for the creation of museums - a time shared by social groups that are excluded from the colonial chronotype” (Brulon 2020, p. 61).

Employees of the Museo MIO en Costa Rica in San José and the University of San José of Costa Rica, in the article “El museo como espacio comunitario and decolonizador: El caso del Museo MIO en Costa Rica y la recuperación de la memoria LGBTIQ+” (Bonilla-Merchav & Brenes 2020, pp. 268-283) are trying to answer the question, what is the role of museums today in the representation a particular community? Do they serve to defend the rights of this community and build a picture of the world that reflects different points of view on a common reality? Do they fulfill the objectives of solidarity and social inclusion?

All LGBTIQ+ museums can be considered as a human rights museum the authors have written. The purpose of such museums is to promote freedom and equality for all people. The MIO Museum is no exception, committed to the liberation of a community that has been silenced and abused. Creating a museum dedicated to the LGBTIQ+ community is a step forward in creating a more just world.

Enrique Sanchez, an MP from the Civic Action Party, who received the support of this community during his election campaign in 2018, initiated the creation of the MIO Museum. This museum is aware of its role as an important public institution that comprehends its social responsibility to create a more open, healthy and just society. It was created to protect the memory and dignity of a particular community.

The MIO Museum is a virtual museum (since the museum does not have a physical location, there is only a website) to restore the memory of the community.

The museum brings to the fore discussions, conversations that few people dare to open themselves to the public.

The promoters of the project are wondered why a museum? CEO J. Sanchez wrote “We thought that we need funds for educational activities, for organizing social dialogue and a space to present the history of relations with the body. And we came to the conclusion that the museum is ideal to be a flexible, educational and playful place” (Bonilla-Merchav & Brenes 2020, p.272). The first step was the creation of a foundation, a legal entity that allowed the museum to comply with the ICOM Code of Ethics. Despite the lack of funds, many people joined the cause, and today the museum works with interdisciplinary professionals.

The museum team has prepared a strategic plan for 2020-2023 with a permanent site expected by 2023 to house permanent and temporary exhibitions showing the history of the LGBTQ+ movement in Costa Rica from 1948 to 2010. The alliance formed with similar museums in the region form the basis of an international network of LGBTIQ+ museums. There are connections with the Chilean “Museum of Di, moving away from the history of the toilet” (Adriazola &...2020, pp.254-267). The edition also presents articles by other authors writing about gay community museums: “Imagine a Museum and Expand Your Audience: Reflections on Queer Matrices” (Nicolau &... 2020, pp. 298-311), “Bazhub Museum: one proposal for a cultural city for LGBTI+ people” (Rodrigues, Morando 2020, pp. 312-323).

After the ICOFOM 2013 conference in Rio de Janeiro's “Special Visitor: Each of Us” it could be assumed that the inclusive right would be used not only by disabled visitors, but also by other communities and societies after museums have proclaimed a policy of inclusion. In our case the basis for bringing people together is the territory that has preserved the imprints of history and the attitude towards the body. Probably, we can expect the emergence of the other grounds for solidarity, association and identification in which flexible form of the museum as a social institution can be used.

The changes in the post-colonial countries

Which of museum forms is developed in post-colonial countries? Is there anything similar to what is happening in Latin America? The editions contain some papers answering these questions. For our point of view, the article has been prepared by Chitima is most interesting. S.S. Chitima, associate professor of Midlands State University-Gweru, presents the results of long-term sociological research of the seven largest museums in Zimbabwe including the Museum of National History, the Zimbabwe Museum of the Humanities. Queen Victoria, National Museum of Transport and Antiquities, Museum of Military History, Police Museum of the Republic of Zimbabwe (Chitima 2021, pp. 67-70). The study used observation, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Sociological survey covered 740 people, including museum staff, university professors, school teachers, journalists, members of various local communities, writers, non-white and black in Zimbabwe. The conclusions of the survey were discouraging: even after 40 years of independence,

state museums in Zimbabwe are perceived as an alien Western institution by native people. Why did the efforts of the government, which invested heavily in museum reforms, not bring results? Firstly, because local communities did not perceive this activity as their own, as a desire to present their values to society and thereby assert their significance in the eyes of other social groups, as the author writes. Secondly, the collections of objects that made up the expositions were based on a set of items that did not belong to them. And if the objects belonged to any community, they were included in everyday forms of life and were not perceived as things worthy of presentation as important values. The researchers came to the conclusion that expositions that built according to European models are poorly perceived by the local population in the post-colonial period. In this case, not only a re-exposure is required, but a serious change in the interpretation of the content. But the most important, as the researcher notes, is the necessity to work for educate the population, otherwise it will not be possible to achieve a positive result, and museums will remain an alien element for the indigenous people of Zimbabwe.

In the context of our reasoning, the conclusion has been reached by a researcher from Zimbabwe is very interesting. He writes that the National Museums of Zimbabwe are still influenced by Western museology and this prevents them from transforming in order to reflect and serve the needs of indigenous communities. He considers it necessary to include all Zimbabweans - black, white, colored - in the discussion of their history and cultural heritage.

That is, the study shows that the Western model of organizing a museum according to the scheme of a professional traditional institution, does not work not only in Zimbabwe but in Brazil too. Thus, Leon P. Bellinha from the University of Rio de Janeiro has described the case of the State Museum of Indigenous Peoples in Rio de Janeiro, which was closed due to lack of visitors (Bellinha 2021, pp. 298-311). The reason was the same: this form of museum does not correspond to the worldview and cultural traditions of indigenous peoples. Whereas experimental museology, that is transformed museum forms, suggest the optimal solution to the problem and can organically fit into the way of life of indigenous peoples. And this is not just a rejection of what the former colonialists has brought, it is a mismatch of cultural codes, a difference in worldview, as written by modern ethnologies who have studied the traditions and rituals of the Indians (Rostova 2020, pp. 731-750).

Let us summarize: in order to fulfill its main mission of broadcasting cultural heritage, a professional museum must be transformed through the involvement of indigenous groups in its activity. But the values of these groups are differed that they require a revision of the fundamental museum code.

Conclusions

What conclusions can be done from this review? Let's clarify what consist of the transformation of the museum's form is today. As we seen the main forms of traditional museum's activity are absent: no collections, no buildings, no staff. Thus, museum team of the

LGBTQ+ in Costa Rica dream about permanent exhibition showing the history of the LGBTQ+ movement in Costa Rica. There are just the same desires according to indigenous communities in Brazil. All the activists from these so-called museums hope to acquire the components of traditional museums: they want to get sites for a permanent exhibition, they intend to amass collections, they are making plans to organize exhibitions. This activity is aimed at the internal tasks of communities, mainly on the development of closer interaction between people and the outline of boundaries for self-identification.

Museums fit into the everyday context, associated with everyday cycles of life. They exist as a list of local pedagogical itineraries (for example Museum of Sao Bento in Rio de Janeiro) or meetings of neighbors, aimed at reproducing traditional knowledge and techniques that ensure procreation ("Museum of Midwives" from the state of Pernambuco). In the case of museums of LGBTQ+ identification is achieved on the basis of the relationship to the body and virtual communication on the psychologically explicit dialogues among members of the LGBTQ community. The priority functions became communication and education, which are modified into storytelling, designed to change the angle of view on the history of the residence place and traditional method of children reproducing, in the first case, and dialogues about one's special physicality, in the second. Museums are being virtualized and use the actionism as a basic form of existence, which brings them even closer to social institutions. Probably, we can expect the emergence of the other grounds for association, solidarity and identification, in which the flexible form of the museum can be used.

As we can see, the current activities of these groups united on any basis, permitted them to call themselves museums, guided by the normative documents of ICOM and UNESCO. That is, the name of the museum is institutionalized by a certain group activity that reveals the most important stage in the development of a traditional museum. Let us emphasize that the museum is institutionalized not by the collection, but by the activities of certain social groups. This initial activity component in the structure of the museum becomes evident during analyzing the stages of construction and is obscured in the resulting stage. That is, not the collections and professional team/staff is an institutionalizing base, but the activity of people united on some values. This allows us to assert that the museum according to the own nature is a social institution.

It can be argued that the situations of the museum's formation described in the issue, are not just a deviation from the norm, they are not unique. In the process of preparing my dissertation "The Museum of Fine Arts as a Social Institution" (Petrunina, 1991), while working in the archives, I found a manuscript showing how in the last third of the 19th century in Russia, after the Zemstvo reform, which created conditions for the development of local self-government, there appeared in many cities' art museums. They are created by the activities of merchants, engineers, teachers, doctors, artists, military men, etc., who initially united in the Society of Art Lovers. About the appearance of

such museums in Astrakhan, Vladimir, Kazan, Saratov, Smolensk, Odessa, Novgorod, Kharkov, etc. wrote in her notes the oldest employee of the Tretyakov Gallery S.I. Bitiutskaya, who studied the features of collecting in Russia (Bitiutskaya 1953, F. 104, d.69 l.6). As you can see, the organization of these museums is based on the activities of social groups united on a certain basis - love for art. That is, motivated activity is the main property of a social institution, which allows us to classify the museum as a social institution, as well as to show its universal nature through the identity of what is happening today in Latin America with what was happening in Russia in the last third of the 19th century.

Let us analyze what is happening today with the museum's collections, these objectified values passed down from generation to generation? We see how "in an effort to reduce social and cultural inequalities" (Shola, 2013, 109-114), museums increase accessibility and develop programs for large groups of visitors. The most common way was the digitalization of collections and the Internet as a communication system. Now, at an accelerating step, we are receiving messages about the digitization and accessibility of the collections through the Internet of the largest museums in the world: the Louvre and the Hermitage, the Metropolitan and the State Tretyakov Gallery, etc. Virtual tours of the museums are gaining distribution.

What does this mean in our context? This indicates that the objectified (*vergegenständlichung*) values that were the basis of the museum's institutionalization are losing their cementing status. This position is now being taken over by activities about the values. And the diversity of the values programs the forms, intensity, strategy and tactics of activity, which will be changed significantly under the pressure of technological innovations, but clearly shows the institutionalizing basis of persons activity for the museum. At the same time, the corpus of the values which is regarded as heritage growing to infinity. How could it have been imagined recently that the attitude towards the own's body of members of the LGBT + would be subjected to value comprehension in the museum paradigm? But this is a modern reality, and we cannot turn a blind eye to it with an honest scientific analysis. And for this position it is necessary to tell gratitude to ICOFOM, which tirelessly shows in its publications the practical development of new museum forms.

Let's return to the discussion about the new definition of the museum that took place during last years. The opposition of the traditional museum as a permanent institution and the comprehends of the museum as a polyphonic space is removed if we embrace the activity about values as the institutionalizing basis of the museum. Activity about the values is a universal characteristic that allows include into the category of museums along with traditional museums open-air museums, and eco-museums, and museums in communities/schools/corporations, and museums on indigenous lands, and mobile museums, and online museums, etc. It is only necessary to include a clarifying notion into the definition of a museum: a social institution. And then the new definition of the museum will, on the one hand, be defined through the term institution, and on

the other hand, to cover the totality of both traditional and paramuseums that is known today. At the same time such a clarification as a social one in the relation to the institution, will allow expanding in the future the innovative variety forms of activity on heritage, without changing the concept of a museum in the definition.

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